

Disrupting Noxious Synergies of Indoor Air Pollutants and their Impact in Childhood Health and Wellbeing using Advanced Intelligent Multi-sensing and Green Interventions

Website Launch

Deliverable number	7.12
Due date	30/11/2022
Nature	DEC
Dissemination level	Public
Work Package	7
Lead Beneficiary	EFA
Contributing Beneficiaries	INLE, NKUA

Disrupting Noxious Synergies of Indoor Air Pollutants and their Impact in Childhood Health and Wellbeing using Advanced Intelligent Multi-sensing and Green Interventions

Table of Contents

Website Launch	1
Project and Document Information	2
Authoring, Revision & QA Information	3
Overview	3
SynAir-G Project Website Briefing	4
Website Evaluation	10

Project and Document Information

Grant Agreement No	101057271	Acronym	SynAir-G
Project Full Title	Disrupting Noxious Synergies of Indoor Air Pollutants and their Impact in Childhood Health and Wellbeing using Advanced Intelligent Multi-sensing and Green Interventions		
Call	HORIZON-HLTH-2021-ENVHLTH-02		
Topic	HORIZON-HLTH-2021-ENVHLTH-02-02	Type of action	RIA
Coordinator	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens		
Start Date	01/09/2022	Duration	48 months
Deliverable	D7.12	Work Package	WP7
Document Type	DEC	Dissemination Level	Public
Lead beneficiary	European Federation of Allergy and Airways Diseases Patients' Associations (EFA)		
Responsible author	Valeria Ramiconi, EFA		
Contractual due date	30/11/2022	Actual submission date	05/12/2022

Authoring, Revision & QA Information

Deliverable Contributors	
Contributor Name	Organisation (Acronym)
Markaya Henderson	European Federation of Allergy and Airways Diseases Patients' Associations (EFA)
Eleanor Morrissey	European Federation of Allergy and Airways Diseases Patients' Associations (EFA)
Angelica Valeria Rossi	European Federation of Allergy and Airways Diseases Patients' Associations (EFA)
Maria Kampa	INLECOM Group (INLE)
Nikos Papadopoulos	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (NKUA)

Version History				
Version	Date	%	Changes	Author
0.1	25/10/2022	25	Selection of webpage layout	EFA
0.2	8/11/2022	50	Changes to photo selection, page organisation and subsections as outlined in website briefing	EFA
0.3	29/11/2022	90	Disclosure requirements modified, twitter feed link changes, paged built out	EFA
1.0	5/12/2022	100	Final version ready for submission	EFA

Quality Control (includes peer & quality reviewing)			
Date	Version	Name (Organisation)	Role & Scope
18/11/2022	0.2	Nikos Papadopoulos, NKUA	General review and alignment with briefing document
22/11/2022	0.2	Maria Kampa, INLE	General review and alignment with briefing document

Overview

EFA completed deliverable 7.12, 'Website Launch,' for Work Package 7, 'Data Management, Guidelines, Dissemination and Exploitation.' The website was launched 01/12/2022 and can be found at the following URL: www.synairg.eu.

Disrupting Noxious Synergies of Indoor Air Pollutants and their Impact in Childhood Health and Wellbeing using Advanced Intelligent Multi-sensing and Green Interventions

The website was built with WordPress and hosted on EFA's OVHcloud account. It will use Google Analytics or a relevant plugin to evaluate website metrics. Website analytics will be shared regularly in the periodic report and reviews.

The website construction followed the guidance of the website briefing below, developed by partner EFA and reviewed by partner INLE with final approval by coordinator NKUA.

The target audiences of the website are researchers, healthcare professionals, policy-makers, patients and civil society at large. Therefore, we wanted to keep the structure "user-friendly", using a lay language without compromising the scientific rigor. We gave emphasis to the news and publications sections, adding also subsections explaining the scientific research and method behind the project, and background information on Indoor air quality, asthma and allergy.

SynAir-G Project Website Briefing

Homepage – www.synairg.eu

Central banner

Disrupting Noxious Synergies of Indoor Air Pollutants and their Impact in Childhood Health and Wellbeing, using Advanced Intelligent Multisensing and Green Interventions

Module: News & Events

Module: Follow SynAir-G

Module: Publications

Contact

Project Coordinator

Nikolaos G. Papadopoulos, MD, PhD
Professor in Allergology- Pediatric Allergology,
Head, Allergy Dpt, 2nd Pediatric Clinic

University of Athens
41, Fidippidou
Athens 115 27 - Greece
tel: +30 (210) 7776964
fax: +30 (210) 777693
ngp@allergy.gr

Disrupting Noxious Synergies of Indoor Air Pollutants and their Impact in Childhood Health and Wellbeing using Advanced Intelligent Multi-sensing and Green Interventions

(Footer)

Privacy and Cookie Policy

Designed by [Altitude Creative Agency](#)

[Insert EU flag]

Funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No 101057271. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

[Page] About - www.synairg.eu/about (not subsections but a page with anchors)

[Subsection] Vision

While the number and types of indoor air pollutants is rising, much is suspected but little is known about the impact of their potentially synergistic interactions, upon human health. Highly susceptible populations include children, allergy and asthma sufferers, and those from low socioeconomic backgrounds, however no specific guidance or interventions are available.

SynAir-G aims to reveal and quantify synergistic interactions between different pollutants affecting health, from mechanisms to real life, focusing on the school setting.

“We will develop a comprehensive and responsive multipollutant monitoring system, advance environmentally friendly interventions, and disseminate the generated knowledge to relevant stakeholders in accessible and actionable formats.”

[Subsection] Objectives

To achieve this vision, SynAir-G will construct and deploy novel and improved sensors of chemical and biological (allergens, microbes) pollutants. These will be tested in a real-world setting, in participating schools of 5 countries around Europe and eventually combined into a multisensing platform.

In the same setting, pollutants will be linked to their sources and two eco-friendly air-purifying devices will be assessed.

Health outcome data will be obtained from children using a gamified application and prospective monitoring, respecting privacy. Highly susceptible children, such as those with allergy or asthma, will act as sentinels to increase sensitivity of the system, that will be able to provide stratified (susceptibility-specific) alerts. Explainable AI will support the near-real time analysis and response.

In parallel, cell and mouse models will evaluate the mechanisms and complex dose-responses of the synergistic parameters. SynAir-G will thus provide FAIR data on air pollutants and their sources, a comprehensive and personalized user-friendly solution to monitoring indoor air quality, and proposals for possible interventions and an improved regulatory framework, robustly supporting the Zero Pollution Action Plan.

SynAir-G is part of a larger cluster of EU funded research projects known as the Indoor air and health cluster where further synergies will be identified.

[Subsection] Governance

[Subsection] Work Packages

WP1: Sensing

Lead: EPFL

WP1 is based on four core goals which focus on developing a novel sensing system targeting atmospheric pollutants in indoor air spaces. The sensing system will be optimized for size, cost-effectiveness, and near-time reporting. The calibration and evaluation of the sensing system will be performed in realistic indoor and outdoor environments.

WP2: Health outcomes

Lead: NKUA

The sensing system developed in WP1 will be the main monitoring tool used achieved the five goals of WP2. The sensing system will be used to establish a multi-pollutant realistic setting, which considers geographical, cultural and socioeconomic cohort of schoolchildren. This will be used to meticulously track biological and chemical indoor air pollutants in the cohort. A gamified e/mHealth tracking system will also be developed to collect participant input/output, and together with the outcomes of the sensing system, they will be utilised to evaluate overall, respiratory, immune and the mental health of the participants, and associate them with the indoor air quality determinants.

WP3: Pollution dynamics

Lead: CHUM

Disrupting Noxious Synergies of Indoor Air Pollutants and their Impact in Childhood Health and Wellbeing using Advanced Intelligent Multi-sensing and Green Interventions

WP3 aims to collect data and model them to identify the sources of chemical and biological indoor air pollutants in and around schools, compare and depict them with indoor and outdoor air quality interactions. The WP3 also aims to link air pollutants in and around schools to their respective sources, and finally, to develop the SynAir-G Inhalation Exposure Assessment Tool.

WP4: In-vitro & in-vivo models

Lead: UER

WP4 aims to measure the effects of pollutant co-exposures on airway and immune cells in-vitro, and to develop a testing system that evaluates the acute synergistic effect of pollutants by using precision-cut lung slices (PCLS). Moreover, it seeks to generate a novel model assessing complex dose-responses of pollutant synergies on airway barrier and immune functions, by using lung organoids. Finally, it targets to validate the synergistic effects of multiple exposures in mouse models in-vivo, to inform quality standards.

WP5: Interventions

Lead: CYRIC

WP5 will deploy the sensing system, developed in WP1, to achieve four goals. The research team will collect the requirements for the integrated system and monitor its integration, and later develop the SynAir-G integrated autonomous sensing platform. Then, it will design and develop diversified mitigation solutions for IAQ improvements, and finally, develop the user interfaces, alert system and modules for device connectivity.

WP6: Intelligence

Lead: UoP

WP6 targets to implement a data ingestion engine, receiving, processing, and forwarding the analysis of high-quality data from sensors, actuators, wearables, questionnaires, and gamified apps. Then, the team of WP6 will compute precise spatiotemporal models of air quality in school classrooms by applying explainable AI for sensor data analysis in addition to mathematical models for pollutant dispersion. Later, it will analyse the interaction effects of chemical, biological pollutants and ambient conditions on health outcomes, by using state-of-the-art AI methods and mathematical modelling. Finally, it will develop and provide a cloud-based platform for comprehensive indoor air quality monitoring and improvement.

WP7: Database & guidelines

Lead: INLE

WP7 aims to organise and deploy optimal communication, dissemination, exploitation and data management of the project.

WP8: Management

Lead: NKUA

Disrupting Noxious Synergies of Indoor Air Pollutants and their Impact in Childhood Health and Wellbeing using Advanced Intelligent Multi-sensing and Green Interventions

WP8 aims to supervise and control the scientific progress of the project; and assess the project in its ethical standard and implement the gender equality policy within the project. The team, in charge of WP8, will manage the project under its financial, administrative and legal aspects, and prepare the progress reports. Moreover, it will guarantee the logistic support and follow-up for the consortium meetings and workshops. Finally, it will be in charge of designing and implementing the networking strategy for the project.

[Page] Partners

Meet the Team

Blocks with partner logos and organisation names

[Page] Activities – www.synairg.eu/activities (not subsections but a page with anchors)

Banner on both subsections

Subscribe to our newsletter for the latest updates, project publications and more.

[text box for email address + subscribe button]

[Subsection] News – www.synairg.eu/activities#news

[article summary feed with links to full articles]

[Subsection] Events – www.synairg.eu/activities#events

[article summary feed with links to full articles]

[Page] Facts - www.synairg.eu/facts (not subsections but a page with anchors)

[Subsection] Asthma and Allergy

[Insert text]

[Subsection] Indoor Air Quality

[Insert text]

[Subsection] Approach & Impact

[Insert text by Work Package]

[Subsection] Longterm Vision

[Insert text]

[Page] Publications - www.synairg.eu/publications

[Subsection] Scientific Articles

[article summary feed with links to external location of articles]

Example:

[Examining patient and professional perspectives in the UK for gene therapy in haemophilia](#)

Woollacott, Ione; Morgan, George; Chowdary, Pratima; O'Hara, Jamie et al.
Part of Haemophilia, p. 588-609, 2022.

[DOI](#)

[Systematic review of quantitative preference studies of treatments for rheumatoid arthritis among patients and at-risk populations](#)

Simons, Gwenda; Caplan, Joshua; DiSantostefano, Rachael L.; Veldwijk, Jorien et al.
Part of Arthritis Research & Therapy, 2022.

[DOI](#) | [Download full text \(pdf\)](#)

Open access

[Case 2 best-worst scaling: For good or for bad but not for both](#)

Soekhai, Vikas; Donkers, Bas; Levitan, Bennett; de Bekker-Grob, Esther W.
Part of Journal of Choice Modelling, p. 100325-100325, 2021.

[DOI](#)

Open access

[Subsection] Roadmap and Guidelines

SynAir-G Roadmap and Guidelines will be developed by consolidating the outcomes and lessons learned from research and piloting activities. The Roadmap will be a comprehensive report including training material, published as a white paper with recommendations to authorities, EU policymakers, and the industry. The report will include a compilation of policies, standards, and technologies used in SynAir-G and a selection of best practices. Guidelines will also target healthcare professionals caring for children with allergy & asthma, sensitizing them to the potential risks of indoor air pollution, the synergies with chemical and biological triggers, and potential mitigation measures.

Stay tuned for Roadmap and Guidelines publications by subscribing to our newsletter and following us on social media.

Website Evaluation

EFA will evaluate website efficacy towards dissemination and communication aims using the following metrics. These metrics will be evaluated for periodic reporting and reviews:

- Website traffic
- Visitor demographic information
- Pageviews per session
- Session duration
- Top pages and traffic sources